

The dawn of the Middle Paleolithic in Atapuerca: The lithic assemblage of TD10.1 from Gran Dolina

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3

4 **Abstract**

5 The Atapuerca localities present evidence of a long series of hominin occupations from
6 the Early Pleistocene onwards and are a key site for understanding the continuity and
7 discontinuity of Western European technological and settlement dynamics. The TD10
8 unit from Gran Dolina is located in the upper part of the sequence and divided into four
9 lithostratigraphic subunits (TD10.4 to TD10.1, from bottom to top) dated between ca. 450
10 ka and ca. 250 ka (MIS 11 to MIS 8). The technological analysis of the lithic assemblages
11 belonging to the TD10.1 sequence aims to determine the trends among its archeological
12 levels and check its relation to Late Middle Pleistocene technological evolution and site
13 functionality. Archeostratigraphic studies have identified several occupation events
14 within its approximately 1.5 m of thickness, whose artifact densities and occupational
15 models differ. However, no remarkable technical differences have been observed among
16 them. Lithic assemblages from those events show more evolved features than other
17 Atapuerca Mode 2 assemblages. These changes are reflected in the selective raw material
18 management strategies; more hierarchized and predetermined reduction methods; and the
19 progressive decrease of large cutting tools in the lithic assemblages with respect to flake
20 tools, the latter defined by a greater typological diversification. These technological
21 changes did not lead to a clear break with respect to previous technological models and
22 were accompanied by other sporadic but significant changes in subsistence and
23 behavioral strategies (bone tools and retouchers; lithic recycling, etc.), which were
24 consolidated during the Middle Paleolithic. Hence, the archeological record from TD10.1

25 subunit of Gran Dolina reflects a local stratigraphic transition from Mode 2 to Mode 3
26 technocomplexes, paralleling that observed in other sites in southwestern Europe.

27

28 **Keywords:** Lithic technology; Middle Paleolithic; Acheulian; Latest Middle Pleistocene;
29 Technical behavior.

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 The archeological sites located in the Trinchera del Ferrocarril (Railway Trench) at
33 Sierra de Atapuerca offer an almost continuous stratigraphic record characterized by the
34 association of lithic, faunal and human fossil remains ranging from 1.2 Ma to 200 ka
35 (Rodríguez et al., 2011). From the technological point of view, the lithic assemblages
36 relate to the Mode 1, Mode 2 and Mode 3 technocomplexes (Clarke, 1969). In particular,
37 the Middle Pleistocene units of the Gran Dolina, Galería, and Sima del Elefante sites
38 present stratigraphic continuity of the Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 11–8 lithic
39 assemblages (Ollé et al., 2013, 2016; García-Medrano et al., 2014, 2015; de Lomberra-
40 Hermida et al., 2015).

41 The TD10 unit contains the final occupational levels from Gran Dolina, dated as late
42 Middle Pleistocene (MIS 11–8), and with lithic assemblages combining Acheulian
43 features along with other more evolved trends (Ollé et al., 2013). In this paper we provide
44 the first analysis of the entire lithic assemblage (>22,000 artifacts) from the TD10.1
45 subunit, belonging to three different archeological levels. Issues relating to changes in
46 raw material procurement strategies, lithic production and shaping processes,
47 occupational patterns, and even subsistence strategies are addressed in order to determine
48 the technological trends of the upper levels of Gran Dolina. Additionally, the differences

49 in occupational patterns and functionality allow us to infer the possible role of those
50 constraints in the technological variability.

51 Comparing the TD10.1 subunit with other Middle Pleistocene records from Atapuerca,
52 as well as other Iberian and Western European sites, should allow us to understand the
53 mechanism behind the progressive appearance of the new technologies and subsistence
54 shifts that would later blossom in the European Middle Paleolithic (e.g., Monnier, 2006;
55 Moncel et al., 2011, 2016; Scott et al., 2011b; Fontana et al., 2013; Kuhn, 2013; Hérison
56 et al., 2016a). From a broader chronological and geographical perspective,
57 contextualizing the TD10.1 subunit should help us understand the rhythms of the
58 technological transition between the technological Modes 2 and 3. The European record
59 reveals complex mechanisms of technological, social and biogeographical diffusion
60 during the Middle Pleistocene, throwing into doubt linear transition models (Arsuaga et
61 al., 2014; Chazan, 2009; Hublin, 2009; Santonja et al., 2016; Carmignani et al., 2017;
62 Bermúdez de Castro et al., 2018).

63

64 *1.1. Gran Dolina site*

65 The Sierra de Atapuerca is situated in a strategic location on the Northern Meseta: the
66 Bureba corridor (Fig.1), communicating the two major river basins on the Iberian
67 Peninsula (Benito-Calvo and Pérez-González, 2015). Atapuerca is a small Cretaceous
68 elevation, circa 25 km² in area and 1050 m asl. Its environment is characterized by diverse
69 biotopes and defined by abundant open spaces, fluvial courses, and valleys offering
70 abundant biotic and abiotic resources within the immediate surroundings of the sites.
71 Analyses of the macro- and micromammal communities point to somewhat stable
72 paleoenvironmental conditions throughout the Pleistocene glacial-interglacial cycles
73 (Rodríguez, 2006; Rodríguez et al., 2011; Blain et al, 2009; 2015; Cuenca-Bescós et al.,

74 2016)—see Supplementary Online Material (SOM) S1). These strategic, ecological and
75 paleoenvironmental features of Atapuerca may explain the long diachrony and intensity
76 of the Pleistocene hominine settlement registered in its stratigraphic records.

77 The endokarst system of the Sierra de Atapuerca is characterized by three main
78 paragenetic levels, related with Pleistocene fluvial base levels. Among them, the
79 Trinchera del Ferrocarril (Railway Trench) cave sites are the most significant. Gran
80 Dolina cave belongs to the intermediate level of the karst system and is infilled by a 19
81 m-thick sedimentary deposit (Ortega et al., 2013; Bermejo et al., 2017). The construction
82 of the railway trench, at the beginning of the 20th century divided the original cave infill
83 into two distinct parts. On the west is the Trinchera Penal (TP) dated to the Early
84 Pleistocene; on the east is the Gran Dolina (TD), originally comprising 11
85 lithostratigraphic units (TD1 to TD11; Gil et al., 1987; Fernández-Jalvo, 1995; Rodríguez
86 et al., 2011; Ollé et al., 2013; van der Made, 2013). The Matuyama-Brunhes boundary is
87 located in the upper part of the TD7 unit, and the sedimentary sequence is divided
88 between the Lower Pleistocene (TD1-2 to TD7) and Middle Pleistocene (TD8 to TD11;
89 Parés and Pérez-González, 1999; Berger et al., 2008; Parés et al., 2013, 2018; Arnold and
90 Demuro, 2015; Arnold et al., 2015).

91

92 *1.2. Lithostratigraphic subunit TD10.1*

93 The TD10 unit comprises a succession of strata associated with gravitational flows
94 (debris fall, debris flow) and fluvial facies (channels, mud flows, etc.) that reaches a
95 thickness of 3 m in the central sector. The TD10 unit is divided into four lithostratigraphic
96 subunits (TD10.4 to TD10.1, from bottom to top) separated by four sedimentary hiatuses
97 (Fig. 2; Campaña et al., 2017; Vallverdú i Poch, 2017). From bottom to top so far seven
98 archeological levels have been identified in the whole TD10 unit. This study focuses only

99 on those from the TD10.1 subunit, which comprises the archeological levels previously
100 known as TD10 (now Lower TD10.1), TD11 (now Upper TD10.1-A), and TD11B (now
101 Upper TD10.1-B; Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004; Terradillos-Bernal, 2010; Ollé et al., 2013;
102 Menéndez-Granda and Vaquero, 2015).

103 The TD10.1 archeological subunit of Gran Dolina is the richest of the Sierra de
104 Atapuerca sites, with more than 22,000 lithic artifacts and 50,300 faunal remains.
105 Archeostratigraphic studies have identified up to 8 layers in TD10.1 with the highest
106 concentrations of lithic and faunal remains being found at the bottom, denominated the
107 TD10.1 ‘bone-bed level’ (Obregón-Labrador, 2012; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015,
108 2017; Fig. 3, SOM Table S1). Most of the archeological remains are concentrated in the
109 northern and eastern sections of the excavated area.

110 The hominin occupations of TD10 took place during a period when the shape of the
111 Gran Dolina cave and its habitable space was in flux, where important erosive events can
112 be identified (Campaña et al., 2017). This changed the space from a relatively closed-in
113 cavity (TD10.4) to an open cave (Lower TD10.1) and, in the final stages, a semi-sheltered
114 environment (Upper TD10.1-A and B; Mallol and Carbonell, 2008). The changes in the
115 habitable conditions are reflected in the horizontal distribution of the archeological
116 remains and activity areas. The sedimentological analysis points to the existence of slow
117 sedimentation rates in the TD10.1 subunit, favoring the formation of micropalimpsests,
118 while in the Upper TD10.1-A and B, sedimentation rates increase. Nevertheless, the
119 scarce incidence of postdepositional and transport dynamics reinforces the spatial
120 integrity of the archeological levels (Mallol and Carbonell, 2008), also corroborated by
121 the taphonomic, archeostratigraphic, and lithic refitting analyses (Blasco, 2011; López-
122 Ortega et al., 2011, 2017, 2019; Obregón-Labrador, 2012; Blasco et al., 2013b;
123 Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015).

124 According to archeostratigraphic studies, throughout the sequence of the TD10.1
125 subunit, residential and short-termed occupations were developed. The base of the
126 TD10.1 subunit is defined by a high density of lithic and faunal remains. It is interpreted
127 as the result of repeated high-intensity residential occupations (base camps), with little
128 evidence of secondary access and modification by carnivores (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al,
129 2015, Ollé et al., 2013). The faunal assemblage is dominated by *Cervus/Dama* sp., *Bison*
130 *schoetensaki*, and *Equus* sp. In the upper part of this subunit, humans may have alternated
131 high-intensity, long-term occupations with sporadic, short-term ones. This hypothesis is
132 based on the identification of several events within the record (i.e., lion hunting; Blasco
133 et al., 2010), the superposition of carnivore marks over anthropogenic ones (Blasco and
134 Rosell, 2009), and the fragmented nature of some of the knapping sequences identified
135 using lithic refits (López-Ortega et al., 2011, 2017). The carnivore activity in the cave is
136 recorded immediately after its abandon by the hominine groups (Blasco et al., 2013b,
137 2013c; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015). In the uppermost levels (Upper TD10.1-A and
138 B) the assemblages are interpreted as the result of repeated low-intensity, short-term
139 occupations (Rosell, 2001; Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004a; Saladié et al., 2018). Throughout
140 the entire TD10.1 sequence, complex behavior is recorded relating to selection, access
141 and consumption of faunal remains, anticipating those strategies established in the
142 European Middle Paleolithic (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015; Blasco et al., 2011, Saladié
143 et al., 2018).

144 For the TD10 unit there are several dates available, based on thermoluminescence
145 (TL), electron spin resonance/uranium-series (ESR/U-Th) and ESR applied to optically
146 bleached quartz grains (ESR-OB), ranging from ca. 450 to 250 ka (MIS 11–8), although
147 there are slight discrepancies between them (Fig. 2; Falguères et al., 1999, 2013; Berger
148 et al., 2008; Moreno et al., 2015). In the TD10.1 subunit there is one average ESR/U-Th

149 date for the top of the sequence (337 ± 29 ka, Upper TD10.1-A and B) and one direct
150 ESR/U-Th date for the ‘bone-bed level’ (TD10.1-h in Lower TD10.1), yielding a value
151 of 379 ± 57 ka (Sample AT9606; Falguères et al., 1999).

152

153 **2. Materials and methods**

154 The entire lithic assemblage from the TD10.1 subunit numbers 22,411 artifacts.
155 Archeostratigraphic work has facilitated the correlation of the materials from the
156 pioneering excavations of Emiliano Aguirre in the uppermost part of the deposit (1984–
157 1989), with those from the stratigraphic test-pits of the 1993 and 1994 seasons, and
158 finally, with the area involved in the 1996–2008 systematic fieldwork campaigns at Gran
159 Dolina (ca. 95 m²). In this sense, the initial study presented in Ollé et al. (2013) is
160 completed. Therefore, for subunit TD10.1, three lithic assemblages have been defined
161 from a diachronic point of view (Fig. 3). The upper lithic assemblages are Upper TD10.1-
162 A (formerly TD11 and TD10.1.a) and Upper TD10.1-B (formerly TD11B). The lower
163 lithic assemblage is labeled Lower TD10.1, formerly published as TD10.1.b (Rodríguez-
164 Álvarez, 2004; Terradillos-Bernal, 2010). All the lithics were analyzed with the exception
165 of those that could not be recovered during the archeological work due to their poor
166 preservation (10.02%), or which are undergoing conservation treatments. Whenever
167 possible, the preliminary field analysis was taken into account.

168 The technological study of the TD10.1 assemblages was based on the attributes
169 established by the Logical Analytical System (LAS; Carbonell et al., 1983, 1992;
170 Rodríguez, 2004a; Ollé et al., 2013). LAS studies the technological processes based on
171 the stage at which the objects were produced during the reduction sequence, on the
172 grounds of the dichotomy between ‘detached products’ (flakes) and ‘flaked products’
173 (cores and retouched tools). In this way, our analysis focused on the raw materials, their

174 distance from the supply area, the representation and technical attributes of each lithic
175 category (pebbles, fractured pebbles, cores, flakes, flake tools, pebble tools, and
176 fragments), the integrity of the reduction sequences, and the main morphotechnical
177 characteristics of the artifacts.

178 The TD10.1 records have yielded six primary raw material groups: Neogene chert,
179 Cretaceous chert, sandstone, quartzite, quartz, and limestone. For this study, several
180 distinct quartzite and quartz varieties were also considered. Quartzites are classified
181 according to their grain size, which plays an important role in fracture patterns and
182 tenacity. However, the degree of metamorphism is another key factor in their isotropy
183 (Pedergrana et al., 2017). In this case, metamorphic and tenacious and quartzose rocks
184 (quartzarenite, orthoquartzite, and metaquartzite) are grouped together as quartzite. The
185 morphostructural groups of quartz are considered according to the presence/absence of
186 grain and plane (de Lombera Hermida et al., 2011): NN (no grain, no plane); NY (no
187 grain, plane); YN (grainy, no plane); and YY (grainy, plane).

188 Knapping methods are defined in this work according to faciality (number of flaked
189 faces), direction of extraction, and arrangement of striking platforms (Rodríguez-Álvarez,
190 2004a, Ollé et al., 2013). Archeologically, these have been identified by technological
191 and diacritic analysis both on cores and, to a lesser extent, products, which are much more
192 difficult to assign. The knapping or exploitation methods considered are: unipolar
193 longitudinal; centripetal; discoidal; predetermined hierarchical centripetal (Levallois);
194 orthogonal, and others (see SOM S2).

195 Shaping processes have been studied in accordance with LAS analytical procedures,
196 which focus on faciality, retouch attributes (portion of the perimeter modified, angle,
197 extent, direction, delineation, and morphology), as well as typological aspects (Laplace,
198 1972). In this case, due to the characteristics of the record, we have considered large

199 cutting tools (LCT) on large flakes (>10 cm; Sharon, 2008) as well as those on smaller
200 blanks. For handaxes and cleavers, classical measurement methods have been adapted
201 and used (García-Medrano et al., 2015).

202 Finally, for a basic metric description, the following size classes have been employed:
203 micro (≤ 20 mm), small (21–60 mm), medium (61–100 mm), and large (>100 mm), in
204 addition to statistical metrics (Ollé et al., 2013). The statistical analysis was performed to
205 identify the relationships between the quantitative and qualitative variables of the lithic
206 assemblages. Chi-square test for independence and non-parametric tests (Kolmogorov-
207 Smirnov and Kruskal-Wallis tests), were completed to compare quantitative data sets
208 using the R software v. 3.3.2 (R Development Core Team, 2016). For the typometric
209 analysis, the null hypothesis is that all rock types are knapped following identical
210 reduction sequences, and therefore identical size distributions can be found for each raw
211 material group. Correspondence analysis were conducted in order to observe the
212 technological trends and differences among the qualitative features and categories of the
213 lithic assemblages. Because of the low number of artifacts from Upper TD10.1-B, this
214 assemblage has not been included in some of the statistical analysis.

215

216 **3. Results**

217 *3.1. Raw materials and lithic categories*

218 The lithic assemblage from the whole TD10.1 subunit numbers 22,411 artifacts
219 (Tables 1–3), the most prolific level being the lowest (Lower TD10.1), which yielded
220 21,522 lithic objects, the majority of which can be related to the TD10.1 ‘bone-bed level’.
221 In the upper assemblages, the number of archeological remains decreases, linked to
222 shorter human occupations. In Upper TD10.1-A and TD10.1-B, only 729 and 138
223 artifacts have been recovered, respectively. We must bear in mind the poor preservation

224 of some of the Neogene chert implements that prevent technological identification of the
225 objects (classified as indet.), which in Upper TD10.1-A account for 27.3% of them.

226 All the raw materials identified in the lithic assemblages can be gathered within the
227 vicinities of the site (García-Antón and Mosquera, 2007; García-Antón, 2010). The major
228 catchment area is basically defined by the Neogene chert blocks found in the Astarician
229 limestone formations and the supply of fluvial materials (sandstones and quartzites) from
230 the Arlanzón Middle Pleistocene terraces (T8_{AZN} +26-35 m y T7_{AZN} +38-42; Moreno et
231 al., 2012), located between 2 and 4 km to the south. The Cretaceous chert from Alto de
232 San Vicente and the quartzitic materials from the Arenas de Utrillas Formation and Vena
233 terraces, to the NE of the Sierra, complement these resources. (SOM S3).

234 TD10.1 includes all the lithic categories, including all the stages related to lithic and
235 tool production. In all the assemblages, detached products predominate over flaked or
236 percussive elements, although there are some minor differences between them. Flaking
237 products (flakes, fragmented flakes, and debris) account for 50–70%, and the
238 representation of whole flakes is relatively constant (32.6–40.3% in Upper TD10.1-B and
239 Lower TD10.1; SOM Fig.S1). The large number of detached products smaller than 20–
240 15 mm in Lower TD10.1 can be explained by the intensity of the reduction processes
241 developed in situ. Additionally, this is complemented by the introduction of medium and
242 large flakes of Neogene chert and fine-grained-quartzite, as also reflected by the refitting
243 studies (López-Ortega et al., 2017). The most significant differences in the lithic
244 assemblages involve the presence of flake tools and percussive elements. The former is
245 better represented in Upper TD10.1-A and B (6.9% and 5.7%, respectively) with respect
246 to Lower TD10.1 (3.4%). These differences between the archeological levels can be
247 related to the functional and occupational patterns developed in the cave. As in the
248 majority of the Sierra de Atapuerca sites, the lithic assemblages of TD10.1 are dominated

249 by varieties of chert, yet they show a wider diversification of raw materials. In Upper
250 TD10.1-A and B chert is the most frequent raw material (65.4% and 63.8%, respectively),
251 while in Lower TD10.1 its presence decreases (60.9%) in favor of the fluvial materials
252 (38.5%). Neogene chert is related to all the reduction and shaping processes, but the
253 presence of Cretaceous chert in the three assemblages is particularly linked to the
254 configuration of light-duty tools and small flakes (Tables 1–3). Only 1.92% of the
255 complete flakes of chert have a significant cortex (>50%) on their dorsal surfaces,
256 pointing to spatial fragmentation of the chaînes opératoires.

257 The presence of fluvial materials is relatively constant. Upper TD10.1-A and B show
258 similar percentages of sandstone (10.8–13.1%) and quartzite (20.3–21.5%), but in Lower
259 TD10.1 the presence of sandstone increases (18.2%) with respect to quartzite (17.2%;
260 Tables 1–3). If we take into account the granulometry, for knapping products larger than
261 20 mm fine-grained varieties of quartzite are better represented in Lower TD10.1 (47.2%)
262 than in Upper TD10.1-A (42.1%). These values are higher than the natural occurrences
263 in the Arlanzón fluvial terraces and closer to the percentages of the Utrillas formation,
264 revealing that the latter were preferentially selected. Sandstones are linked to flake
265 production, LCTs, and, along with coarse-grained quartzites, percussive elements. Other
266 raw materials are scarcely represented (<1%). Quartz plays only a relatively
267 complementary role in the Lower TD10.1 assemblage (3.4%) with a significant presence
268 of high-quality blanks (NN and NY groups, 60.5% and 35.9%, respectively), once again
269 pointing to their preferential acquisition from the Utrillas outcrops.

270

271 3.2. *Percussive elements*

272 Unknapped pebbles and cobbles comprise, coarse-grained quartzite, sandstone,
273 limestone and, to a lesser extent, quartz. These raw materials were selected because of

274 their morphology (oval and spheroid cobbles) and higher tenacity. Cobbles with clear
275 percussion marks (Bnb) are larger than those without them (Bna), ranging between 50–
276 100 mm in length, 39–85 mm in width, and 20–61 mm in thickness (Kruskal-Wallis test,
277 for length: $\chi^2 = 6.35$, $p = 0.041$; width: $\chi^2 = 10.5$, $p = 0.0052$; thickness: $\chi^2 = 8.9372$, $p =$
278 0.01146 ; SOM Fig. 2), which means a statistical significance for the size selection of both
279 categories. Because of their size (most are longer than 81 mm), weight, and morphology,
280 these implements could be related to flake production. Hammerstones shorter than 50 mm
281 are very scarce and could be linked to retouching processes. The bigger and heavier ones
282 could also have been used in bone fracturing and marrow acquisition (Blasco et al.,
283 2013b; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015), which is well documented at the site, but we
284 cannot rule out a relationship with other pounding activities involving different organic
285 materials (Mora and de la Torre, 2005; Benito-Calvo et al., 2017). Their greater
286 representation in the Upper TD10.1-A and B assemblages (3.7% and 2.9%) with regard
287 to Lower TD10.1 (0.47%) is here interpreted as these activities being more important in
288 the upper occupations.

289 Finally, one of the most significant features of these materials (especially quartzite) is
290 their versatility in the lithic reduction sequences. Because of their tenacity and inner
291 structure, they are able to absorb the intense energy produced during percussion, allowing
292 them to serve as blanks for subsequent knapping sequences ($n = 50$; see section 3.5).

293

294 *3.3. Exploitation methods and products*

295 The presence of cores is restricted in percentage terms (1.1%, 1.4%, and 2.7% from
296 Lower TD10.1, Upper TD10.1-B, and Upper TD10.1-A, respectively), particularly given
297 the overrepresentation of small flakes, testifying to the importance of the exploitation
298 activities at the site. In Upper TD10.1-B only two cores were recorded, revealing

299 unstructured knapping. In terms of size, the cobble cores and flake cores from Lower
300 TD10.1 ($n = 127$) only differ in their thickness (Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney: $W = 6911$, p
301 < 0.05), showing that the reduction intensity and strategies were independent of the blank-
302 type employed (SOM Table S2).

303 Bifacial strategies were preferentially applied (Lower TD10.1: 79.9%; Upper TD10.1-
304 A: 75%) over unifacial strategies, and only the Lower TD10.1 assemblage includes
305 trifacial and multifacial approaches (7.3%). One large trifacial core of Neogene chert in
306 Lower TD10.1 could be related to the production of large flakes (>100 mm; Fig. 4.A. In
307 Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A the cores are in advanced (41.1% and 26.7%,
308 respectively) or final reduction stages (51.42% and 46.7%, respectively) showing reduced
309 cortical surfaces. The higher percentage of initial cores (26.7%) and the more important
310 role of expedient methods in the upper levels could be related to less intensity of hominine
311 occupations (Fig. 4; SOM Fig. S3).

312 The technological study of the lithic assemblages and diacritic reading of the cores and
313 flaking products has allowed the identification of six main knapping methods,
314 predominating the centripetal schemes. These must be adapted to the morphometry of the
315 blank, raw material type, reduction stages, and flaking objectives. LCT production has
316 only been identified by its final products (handaxes and cleavers).

317 The unipolar longitudinal reduction method It is especially associated with quartzite,
318 sandstone cobbles, and the reduction of large blocks of Neogene chert, taking advantage
319 of natural striking platforms or fracture planes (7.35%, $n = 18$) . As the reduction
320 sequences advance, bifacial and bidirectional/peripheral reduction is applied, but always
321 keeping a preferential flaking surface. Flaked products usually display cortical or
322 unifacted striking platforms and cortical backs opposite good lateral or distal cutting
323 edges.

324 The orthogonal method It is preferentially applied to Neogene and Cretaceous chert,
325 through bi- and multidirectional abrupt series and, occasionally, alternating between
326 flaked and flaking surfaces with core rotation (14.7%, $n = 36$) . The products are short
327 and wide, quadrangular, and have thick striking platforms. This method was applied to
328 maximize raw material use and, consequently, those in their final reduction stages are
329 almost exhausted.

330 The centripetal method It was widely applied in all the lithic assemblages and using all
331 raw materials (43.7%, $n = 107$) . The reduction sequences are defined by peripheral and
332 secant removals and more intense surface reduction. This method was performed right
333 from the beginning of the knapping process (as evidenced by large cores, i.e., SOM Fig.
334 S4), with peripheral, bifacial, and alternate knapping increasing as the reduction
335 sequences advanced.

336 One of the main features of the TD10.1 assemblages is the significance of the
337 centripetal hierarchical management of the knapping surfaces. 40% of the centripetal
338 cores in Lower TD10.1 and 25% in Upper TD10.1-A display a preferential flaking surface
339 (mean number of removals = 5.7), while the second surface involved preparing the
340 striking platform for subsequent radial exploitation of the main exploitation surface
341 (mean number of removals = 3.5; Fig. 5; SOM Fig. 4). This pattern is more evident on
342 flake cores (49.2%) due to their morphological features. Finally, no evidence has been
343 found of striking surface shaping. In that sense, there was no volume control or final
344 product predetermination, in contrast to the features of the classical Levallois method
345 (Boëda, 1994).

346 The discoidal method It was preferentially applied to Neogene chert, sandstone, and fine-
347 grained quartzite (8.2%, $n = 20$) . Within the variability observed in this method,
348 hierarchized discoidal cores have also been identified (Boëda, 1993; Terradas, 2003). The

349 presence of predetermined products and large cores corresponding to initial reduction
350 stages shows that this method was applied from the very beginning of the core reduction
351 (Fig. 4).

352 The bifacially predetermined hierarchical centripetal method This method (i.e., Levallois:
353 6.9%, $n = 17$; Fig. 5) was applied to good-quality Neogene and Cretaceous chert,
354 sandstone, and fine-grained quartzite. Exceptionally, one hierarchized core of quartz has
355 been recorded from Upper TD10.1-A (Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004a). Several knapping
356 strategies have been identified: centripetal recurrent ($n = 4$); linear with preferential
357 removal ($n = 7$); and hierarchized in the final stages ($n = 2$). Although these fit within the
358 classical Levallois method, the centripetal hierarchized cores from Lower TD10.1 and
359 Upper TD10.1-A are defined by scarce configuration of the laterotransverse convexities
360 of the flaking surfaces (surface volume) and striking platforms (Menéndez and Vaquero,
361 2015). Only 2.7% of the cores show striking platform shaping, consistent with the lack
362 of predetermined products and low percentage of multifaceted platforms (ca. 4%) in the
363 lithic assemblages.

364 In Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A we consider that the centripetal
365 hierarchized method was not focused on achieving predetermined and standardized
366 products (classical Levallois flakes), but rather on maximising the raw material through
367 either recurrent centripetal strategies or preferential removals, especially on those cores
368 in advanced exploitation stages (Fig. 5). This knapping method is analogous to those
369 described in other European late Middle Pleistocene assemblages as ‘proto-Levallois’ or
370 ‘prepared platform cores’ (Kuhn, 1995; White and Ashton, 2003) and falls within the
371 variability documented at other classic Late Pleistocene sites (i.e., Vaquero et al, 2012b).
372 Its presence in TD10.1 represents one of the most progressive technological features with

373 respect to other Middle Pleistocene assemblages from the Sierra de Atapuerca sites (Ollé
374 et al., 2013, 2016; García-Medrano et al., 2015).

375 Others Finally, unstructured cores have been defined by the expedient reduction either on
376 initial cores (test cores) or for their final exploitation (exhausted cores, etc.; 13.27%, $n =$
377 30).

378 There is a massive presence of flaking products in all the assemblages, but decreasing
379 in time (69.9%, 60.9%, and 57.3%, from bottom to top). In terms of size, several
380 differences can be observed between the archeological levels if we consider only
381 complete flakes (BP). The high incidence of flaking products smaller than 20 mm in the
382 Lower TD10.1 assemblage (70.7%), in addition to broken flakes, flake fragments, and
383 debris evidences the intensity of the exploitation processes developed in situ (Fig. 6). In
384 contrast, in Upper TD10.1-A and B, medium and large flakes (>60 mm long) predominate
385 (>60%), pointing to the introduction of previously knapped material into the site and a
386 mixture of flake sizes linked to the different knapping methods (Fig. 6; SOM Tables S3
387 and S4).

388 From a morphotechnical perspective, the detached products in the TD10.1
389 assemblages are consistent with the exploitation strategies defined for the cores. Most of
390 the specimens retain no cortex on their dorsal faces (79.2%, 79.1%, and 78.3%, from
391 bottom to top) or butts (85.3%, 88.8% and 82.6%, respectively) while only 1.5–1.7%
392 have complete cortical surfaces (particularly sandstone and quartzite). Consequently,
393 unifaceted butts predominate (ranging from 56.5–69.2%) over bifaceted ones (13.4–
394 22%), while the low percentages of multifaceted butts (4–4.35%) reflect the summary
395 configuration of striking platforms. The striking platforms are wide and relatively thin
396 (7–8 mm), even thinner in the Cretaceous chert flakes (5 mm).

397 The intensity of reduction sequences is reflected by the predominance of non-cortical
398 dorsal surfaces and a high mean number of dorsal removals (>3). The products from
399 Upper TD10.1-B follow a different tendency, with a higher percentage of cortical surfaces
400 (13%) and a lower mean number of removals, reflecting more expedient knapping
401 methods in this level (SOM Fig. S5A, B). Although the TD10.1 assemblages are defined
402 by a greater predominance of small and medium-sized flakes with respect to other Middle
403 Pleistocene sites from Atapuerca (Ollé et al., 2013), there is no morphological
404 standardization of the flaking products. Exploitation strategies were aimed at obtaining a
405 wide morphological diversity of detached products, trapezoidal, rectangular, and
406 triangular morphologies being the most abundant (never exceeding 20–30%). Levallois
407 flakes are flat and elongated, displaying centripetal or longitudinal patterns on their dorsal
408 faces and having peripheral cutting edges (Figs. 7d and 8e, f). Some of these products
409 seem to have been transported from other locations, particularly those from the Upper
410 TD10.1-A set (López-Ortega et al, 2017).

411 We must bear in mind that there might be a technological continuum between these
412 knapping methods, according to their degree of reduction. The presence of large and
413 initial cores corresponding to each method show that structured reduction sequences are
414 applied since the initial stages of knapping. However, as reduction sequences advance,
415 there might be a transfer among them. This continuum is especially observed between
416 bifacial centripetal, discoidal and hierarchized centripetal cores. The diversification of
417 exploitation strategies in TD10.1 must be understood in terms of lithic efficiency rather
418 than morphological standardization. More suitability between the knapping method and
419 raw material worked is reflected by an increase in the production of cutting edges per kg
420 of raw material on retouched and unretouched implements, presenting important

421 differences with respect to other Atapuerca Middle Pleistocene sets (Terradillos-Bernal
422 and Rodríguez, 2012; Terradillos-Bernal and Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2017; SOM Table S5).

423

424 *3.4. Shaping sequences and large cutting tools production*

425 In the upper levels of TD10.1 shaped tools are proportionally better represented than
426 in Lower TD10.1 (3.3%, 5.7%, and 6.8%, from bottom to top). Nevertheless, the presence
427 of retouching flakes and lithic refits in the lowermost layer points to the importance of
428 shaping activities. In TD10.1 there is apparently a mixture of typical Acheulian forms
429 (handaxes, cleavers, large shaped tools) and standardized flake artifacts, closer to the
430 Mode 3 toolkit, although the latter clearly dominate (Ollé et al., 2013; Mosquera et al.,
431 2013). At the same time, there is a diversification of raw materials involved in the shaping
432 processes and Cretaceous chert became the material of choice for flake tools (Tables 1–
433 3). Similarly to other Atapuerca Mode 2 sites, shaping strategies focused on the
434 production of small and medium flake tools and few large shaped tools or LCTs (García-
435 Medrano et al., 2015). Consequently, flakes are the preferential blanks (93.25%).

436 Large shaped tools and large cutting tools As usual in Atapuerca, choppers are scarce,
437 and only 4 of such tools have been recovered (3 from Lower TD10.1 and 1 from Upper
438 TD10.A).

439 LCTs, in turn, are scarce compared to other Middle Pleistocene records from
440 Atapuerca, and they account for just 3.22% of the retouched tools in Lower TD10.1 and
441 10.41% in Upper TD10.1-A (0.11% and 0.65% in absolute terms). In total, 25 artifacts
442 can be linked to LCT production sequences, 5 of them from Upper TD10.1-A. Large
443 flakes (71.4%) of sandstone (50%), quartzite (28.6%), and Neogene chert (21.4%) were
444 preferred rather than cobbles.

445 Handaxes ($n = 12$) and their by-products (bifacial rough-outs, fragmented handaxes, n
446 = 7) account for over 70.3% of the LCTs. One of their main characteristics is that they
447 are in the initial rough-out or shaping stages. Only in 7.1% of cases configuration series
448 affect the entire perimeter of the piece. The handaxes from Lower TD10.1 are smaller
449 than those from Upper TD10.1A, with greater size heterogeneity (SOM Table S6), and
450 other Atapuerca assemblages. In addition, there is a clear tendency towards more pointed
451 shapes from the Lower to the Upper sequence of TD10.1. The TD10.1 handaxes present
452 sinuous edges, cortical reserves on their surfaces, and asymmetrical volumes. In some
453 cases, hinged terminations and dulling can be seen (Fig. 9). Consequently, they display
454 no clear morphological standardization. In contrast, no significant differences were noted
455 in their metric data ($p > 0.05$), pointing to the existence of standardized templates that
456 had not yet been fully realized in these implements.

457 The initial management (roughing-out) and shaping of the bifacial tools along with by-
458 products related to handaxe production (bifacial thinning flakes, and bifacial apices) point
459 to the spatial fragmentation of their production sequences. Although large blanks were
460 probably produced in the source areas, the absence of thinning and finished handaxes may
461 point to their high degree of mobility beyond the site, in contrast to the production and
462 utilization patterns observed in Units GII and GIII at Galería. On the other hand, the lower
463 degree of LCT standardization, in addition to their increased rarity, could reflect a
464 decreasing interest in the final morphology of these implements (García-Medrano et al.,
465 2015; Ollé, 2013).

466 Finally, only three cleavers have been recovered (Fig. 10). These implements show a
467 distal straight edge and some lateral retouching to morphologically adapt them, and
468 according to Tixier's (1956) typology, they are ascribed to Types I and II. In one case, a
469 stepped retouch was performed on one of the lateral edges, yielding a convex form

470 equivalent to a Quina sidescraper and showing use wear traces. The distal edge presents
471 large macro-scars on both faces, pointing to the use of the tool for chopping (Pedergrana
472 and Ollé, 2019). The superimposition of the lateral retouching on the scars from the distal
473 edge, in addition to the presence of retouching flakes belonging to the same raw material
474 unit, indicate that the lateral retouching took place in situ, and was subsequent to the
475 configuration of the cleaver. This particular case could be interpreted as recycling of the
476 cleaver for a different functional purpose than that originally planned.

477 Flake tool configuration Shaping processes in the three archeological levels clearly
478 focused on the production of small flake tools. The size analysis of the retouched flakes
479 shows preferential use of small and medium-sized blanks (ranging from 34 to 54 mm),
480 larger than the mean length of the flakes (SOM Table S7) and preference for flakes
481 without cortex, so produced during advanced stages of cores reduction. In Lower TD10.1
482 (the only representative sample) there are significant differences between the raw
483 materials worked with regard to their length (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 86,133$, $df = 4$, $p =$
484 <0.0001), width ($\chi^2 = 69.938$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.0001$), and thickness ($\chi^2 = 22.174$, $df = 4$, $p <$
485 0.0001), which rules out size standardization. Sandstone and quartzite tools are generally
486 larger than others raw materials. Retouching is usually unifacial, direct, and it is focused
487 on one segment of the blank through a simple and semiabrupt series of short removals.

488 In Lower TD10.1, the tools present a higher retouching intensity focused on modifying
489 the edges and morphology of tools (convergent tools, sidescrapers, etc.; Fig. 10).
490 Sidescrapers with stepped retouching are particularly associated with fined-grained raw
491 materials like quartzite and Cretaceous chert (Fig. 11). The presence of retouching flakes
492 corresponding to the so-called Quina retouching (Bourguignon, 2001) strengthens the
493 idea that these shaping processes were performed in situ. In contrast, in Upper TD10.1-
494 A and B assemblages, the shaping processes were quite expedient and short, defined by

495 their immediacy in achieving cutting edges. Unlike the Lower TD10.1 assemblage, in
496 Upper TD10.1-A there is no significant relationship between the raw materials worked
497 and the tool type ($\chi^2= 77.003$, $df = 65$, $p = 0.1465$). Additionally, the length of the
498 retouched flakes in the Upper TD10.1-A assemblage presents a bimodal distribution
499 (SOM Fig. S6), pointing to the introduction of larger, preshaped tools into the site
500 (curated tools).

501 Typologically, the upper layers are defined by reduced variability and low number of
502 flake tools ($n = 42$ and $n = 7$, respectively; Table 4), dominating sidescrapers and
503 denticulate groups (totaling 75% and 70% in Upper TD10.1-A and B, respectively). In
504 contrast, Lower TD10.1 offers the highest typological variety of all the Atapuerca records
505 (Ollé et al., 2013). There is an expansion of tool morphotypes and morphopotentialities,
506 pointing to the occurrence of varied activities at the site, consistent with a residential
507 occupational model (Table 5; Fig. 10). The denticulate group (57.8%) is much more
508 frequent than sidescrapers (35.7%) and other groups, particularly pointed tools (2.4%).

509 One of the main characteristics of Lower TD10.1 with respect to the other Middle
510 Pleistocene sites at Atapuerca is the special relevance of convergent and pointed tools
511 (sensu Moncel et al., 2009), most of which are small (<50 mm long): denticulate points
512 (D14 + D24 = 4.67%), points (P11 + P21 = 2.4%), and some convergent sidescrapers
513 (R23 = 2.1%; Fig. 11). These artifacts are defined by the bilateral shaping of the tip,
514 whether their technological and morphological axis is coincident (convergent) or not
515 (dejété). The morphopotential aspect of these objects prevails over their typology, and no
516 size standardization has been observed (i.e., Chacón et al., 2016). Some pieces presenting
517 lateral and distal retouching associated to natural trihedrals ($n = 11$) can be included in
518 this category. In some cases, volumetric or thinning retouching on the ventral faces was
519 performed to facilitate prehension or hafting, as described for one object from Lower

520 TD10.1 (ATA99-I15-92; Fig. 12B). Based on the use-wear features we must consider the
521 assumed multifunctional nature and versatility of these implements (Moncel et al, 2009).

522

523 *3.5. Other technological features of the TD10.1 assemblages*

524 The TD10.1 assemblage presents certain progressive technical aspects,
525 complementary to the lithic production processes, some of which are observed for the
526 first time in the Atapuerca record.

527 Hafting Evidence of composite tools at Lower TD10.1 is provided by three quartzites
528 (Pedergnana and Ollé, 2019; Fig. 12). These artifacts are very well preserved, not being
529 affected by postdepositional modifications. The first one is a triangular small-sized
530 denticulate (ATA99-I15-92; Fig. 12B) that shows wear traces on the tip connected to a
531 longitudinal action (sawing) on a hard material. Hafting traces are located on the proximal
532 portion of the tool. The second (ATA00-N20-66; Fig 12A) is a convergent scraper that
533 shows traces pointing to hide scraping, and hafting traces in the proximal end, which had
534 been likely modified to fit a handle. The third artifact bearing hafting traces (ATA04-
535 K21-132) is a sidescraper where bone sawing was observed on the retouched edge, while
536 a notch was produced on the distal end likely to fit a handle.

537 There is an additional artifact with hafting traces coming from the TD10.2 unit (Fig.
538 12C). It is an endscraper made of Cretaceous chert (ATA93-H18-9). Although it was
539 previously published as belonging to the Lower TD10.1 level (Márquez et al., 2001;
540 Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004b), after the archeostratigraphic revision it was reassessed as
541 TD10.2. The distal edge shows strong modification, in the form of continuous rounding,
542 an abraded surface, and transverse striations, linked to hide scraping. Originally, the
543 possible addition of abrasives was proposed (Márquez et al. 2001), but this hypothesis
544 should be reviewed. Furthermore, the stepped retouching of the distal edge could be

545 interpreted as tool resharpening. Evidence of hafting involves flake thinning on the
546 medial portion of both lateral edges. Additionally, some hafting wear has been identified,
547 with spots of leveled microrelief (flat polishes) and short striations.

548 Lithic recycling Events of lithic recycling have been documented in the Lower TD10.1
549 ($n = 48$) and Upper TD10.1-A assemblages ($n = 2$), mostly on quartzite artifacts because
550 of the tenacious nature of the material and its good preservation. Several scenarios can be
551 defined within this category (Amick, 2007; Vaquero et al., 2015). One of the most
552 common situations is the reuse of hammerstones as blanks for lithic production. In several
553 cores ($n = 19$), detached products ($n = 19$), and shaped elements ($n = 12$), the cortical
554 reserves preserve pits and battering marks. One of the most illustrative examples is one
555 lithic refit in Lower TD10.1, where the core and an initial fragmented flake present heavy
556 percussion marks on their margins (Fig. 13A), showing that the long exploitation
557 sequence was subsequent to its previous use as a percussive element. Two cleavers also
558 show clustered pits on their cortical surfaces.

559 In contrast, some knapped elements were used as hammerstones. In TD10.1, 10 lithic
560 elements show percussion marks on their dorsal surfaces, scars, and ridges. The pits are
561 clustered along the internal ridges and on the inner part of the blanks, differing from
562 marks considered to show erroneous blows during knapping events (Fig. 13B; Thiébaud
563 et al., 2010). Based on the light development of percussion marks, these could be related
564 to retouching activities. Interestingly, their mean size is smaller than the cobbles used as
565 hammerstones and similar to the small lithic retouchers (SOM Fig. S7). Given the scarcity
566 of the latter in the assemblages, these could be interpreted as part of an opportunistic and
567 supplementary strategy for lithic configuration.

568 The visibility of examples of lithic recycling (cores reused as tools, etc.) in TD10.1 is
569 quite restricted due to the preservation conditions of the local chert (well-developed

570 patina). Only one recycled patinated element has been observed. It is a retouched tool
571 made of the allochthonous chert (Villagonzalo-Perdernalles) that was imported already
572 reshaped, showing an important temporal and spatial fragmentation of its use history
573 (García-Antón, 2016). Despite the relative representation of cores-on-flakes with
574 unstructured scars and Kombewa products in TD10.1 that could be interpreted as cores-
575 on-flakes/flaked-flakes (COF/FFs; Assaf et al., 2015; Parush et al., 2015), the absence of
576 patinas prevents us from distinguishing whether they represent elements related to
577 recycling or ramified production (Bourguignon et al., 2004).

578 Bone tools and retouchers They can also be considered a recycling activity (Rosell et al.,
579 2015). On the one hand, two bone fragments were knapped on their sides to generate a
580 cutting edge, reproducing the morphotypes of their lithic counterparts (sidescrapers;
581 Rosell et al., 2011). On the other hand, seven bone remains from Lower TD10.1 present
582 percussion marks related to their use as retouchers. All except one element are related to
583 the TD10.1 bone-bed level (Blasco et al., 2013a; Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015). Neither
584 taxonomic selection nor morphological modification has been observed on these elements
585 (by-products of butchery activities). All but one presents a single active zone, located at
586 the distal end, where pits, V-shaped scores, and some hatched and scaled areas can be
587 seen. In one case, residues of Neogene chert were observed within the pits, implying their
588 direct relationship with lithic shaping processes (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2013; Fig.
589 14A–C). The intensity and type of percussion marks on the bone retouchers seem to
590 exclude them from having been used to perform Quina retouching (Mallye et al., 2012).
591 Indeed, these tools would have principally been related to short configuration sequences.
592 These features are consistent with the presence of tools with marginal retouching, scalar
593 superimposition, and small configuration flakes presenting rectangular and trapezoidal
594 shapes, hinges, and step terminations (Bourguignon et al., 2004; Fig. 14D, E). In this

595 sense, the bone retouchers are interpreted as part of an opportunistic strategy for
596 resharpening lithic implements in order to extend their functional life. Their presence in
597 the TD10.2 subunit and the upper part of Lower TD10.1 show that this is a recurrent
598 technical behavior for the final Middle Pleistocene hominines of Atapuerca (Rodríguez
599 Hidalgo et al., 2015; 2017; Blasco et al., 2013c).

600

601 **4. Discussion**

602 *4.1. The lithic assemblages from TD10.1 in the Atapuerca record*

603 The hominin occupations of the TD10.1 subunit took place at a time during which the
604 excavated area of the cavity was changing morphologically from a cave entrance-hall to
605 a more open environment, undoubtedly conditioning the inhabitable space and occupation
606 patterns (Mallol and Carbonell, 2008). Nevertheless, from a technological point of view,
607 there is clearly continuity in the production and shaping strategies of the assemblages
608 that, despite the functional differences, may imply a cultural continuity of the groups that
609 inhabited the Sierra de Atapuerca throughout the MIS 11–8.

610 Compared to other Middle Pleistocene records from Atapuerca, the lithic assemblages
611 from the TD10.1 subunit show a mixture of technical elements already observed in the
612 underlying Mode 2 assemblages of Gran Dolina (TD10.2, TD10.3) as well as the nearby
613 sites of Galería and Sima del Elefante (Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004b; Mosquera et al., 2013;
614 Ollé et al., 2013; García-Medrano et al., 2015; de Lombera-Hermida et al., 2015), in
615 addition to other technological innovations, lending them a more progressive character.

616 From the technological point of view, the Lower TD10.1 assemblage is defined by a
617 diversification in the raw materials worked, reflecting a systematic and structured
618 exploitation of the abiotic resources (García-Antón, 2010, 2016). Resources located
619 within the immediate vicinity of the site, no further than 4 km away, fully satisfy the lithic

620 demand. Although the complementary nature of these catchment areas is also observed
621 in other assemblages from Atapuerca (e.g., Galería GII-GIII; Sima del Elefante TE18-19,
622 TD6), the incidence of quartzites and, especially, quartz from the Utrillas Formation is
623 highly significant in the Lower TD10.1 assemblage (Mallol, 1999; Terradillos and
624 Rodríguez Álvarez, 2014; García-Antón, 2016; Pedergnana et al., 2017). In this sense,
625 there is direct and specialized procurement of resources whose functional and technical
626 quality (granulometry, workability, etc.) complements the lithologies available from the
627 Arlanzón terraces. The presence of fewer Utrillas materials in the Upper TD10.1-A and
628 B assemblages, the sources of which are more distant, indicates more expedite and
629 generalist procurement strategies for these levels.

630 In the TD10.1 subunit, the management of the lithic resources involved optimizing
631 raw materials by implementing strategies based on more efficient selection of blank
632 quality, transport and use than evidenced at other Atapuerca and Middle Pleistocene sites
633 (i.e., Serangeli and Conard, 2015; Douglass et al., 2016; Santagata et al., 2017). This
634 optimization is reflected in the greater production of usable edges per kg of raw material
635 in Lower TD10.1 (Terradillos and Rodríguez Álvarez, 2014). The spatial fragmentation
636 of the 'chaîne opératoire' of certain raw material varieties (i.e., quartz), as well as the
637 presence of imported flakes and curated tools, show long-term planning in lithic tool
638 production according to technical and functional requirements (Moncel et al., 2008a, b,
639 2014; Turq et al., 2013). This strategy was a response to planned procurement, selection,
640 and transport decisions, analogous to those documented in the faunal management
641 (Blasco, 2011; Blasco et al., 2013c; Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015).

642 The Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A assemblages are characterized by a wide
643 variety of exploitation methods. The differences observed between the lithic assemblages
644 can be explained by the sporadic/short-term (Upper TD10.1-A and B) or intensive, long-

645 term nature (Lower TD10.1) of the hominin occupations. In general, the reduction
646 strategies are defined by the centripetal reduction conceptual framework, based on the
647 bifacial, peripheral, and secant management of core volumes, very similar to the discoidal
648 concept (Boëda, 1993; Mourre, 2003; Peresani, 2003). However, classical discoidal and
649 bifacial centripetal hierarchized (Levallois) methods are also applied. In Lower TD10.1
650 (the most representative from the quantitative point of view), there is a significant
651 correlation between the exploitation methods and the raw material to be worked ($\chi^2 =$
652 72.009, $df = 40$; $p < 0.001$). If we consider the cores from Lower TD10.1 and Upper
653 TD10.1-A, on the whole this relationship is maintained ($\chi^2 = 78.23$, $df = 40$, $p = < 0.001$;
654 SOM Fig. S8). Therefore, despite the divergence observed between the two assemblages
655 resulting from different functional purposes and occupational intensities, the suitability
656 of knapping methods, raw material, and final products is maintained through time,
657 pointing to the fact that the hominine groups from both levels shared the same conceptual
658 scheme (Rodríguez-Álvarez 2004a).

659 Consequently, in TD10.1 planned and structured exploitation strategies were applied
660 according to raw material and final product characteristics, as well as occupational
661 patterns, but involving certain novelties with respect to the Mode 2 assemblages from
662 Atapuerca. Firstly, while the TD10.1 levels consolidate the tendency observed in the
663 Galería sequence (particularly the GIII assemblage), where the centripetal method is
664 generalized (García-Medrano et al., 2015; Ollé et al., 2013; Rodríguez-Álvarez, 2004a;
665 Terradillos, 2010), one of its main features is the importance of hierarchized flaking
666 surfaces. In almost 40% of the centripetal cores the roles between the striking and flaking
667 surfaces are maintained during the reduction sequence.

668 Secondly, Levallois cores and products are scarce, but significant from a qualitative
669 perspective, as these represent the first appearance of ‘prepared core technologies’

670 (Hopkinson et al., 2013) in the Atapuerca records. Nevertheless, the TD10.1 lithic
671 assemblages cannot be classified as typical Levallois, as other final Middle Pleistocene
672 levels are (Moncel et al., 2011). Their presence in all the TD10.1 layers demonstrates the
673 well-implemented application of this method in the Late Middle Pleistocene communities
674 of Atapuerca, but it should be understood as a strategy for maximizing raw materials and
675 obtaining medium-sized and large products (Van Peer, 1992; White and Ashton, 2003),
676 rather than for morphological predetermining and standardizing of the detached products
677 (Eren and Lycett, 2012).

678 Traditionally, the emergence of the Levallois methods is considered a technological
679 milestone of the early Middle Paleolithic (Hopkinson et al., 2013; Moncel et al., 2005;
680 Villa, 2009). Its first appearance in Europe dates to MIS 12–10 (Tuffreau et al., 2008;
681 Antoine et al., 2016; Lamotte and Tuffreau, 2016; Soriano and Villa, 2017; Picin, 2018).
682 However, its expansion across Europe seems to have occurred in an irregular and patchy
683 manner from MIS 9 onwards (White and Ashton, 2003; Scott et al., 2011b; Terradillos-
684 Bernal and Díez-Fernández-Lomana, 2012; Fontana et al., 2013; Adler et al., 2014;
685 Ashton, 2016; Doronichev, 2016; Hérison et al., 2016a; Carmignani et al., 2017; Picin,
686 2017; Moncel et al., 2020).

687 Nevertheless, the emergence and generalization of prepared core technologies in the
688 TD10.1 subunit is not the only remarkable change recorded in the technological dynamics
689 with respect to the Mode 2 sites. In the three lithic assemblages considered here,
690 production clearly predominates over shaping processes. The latter were aimed at the
691 production of small and medium-sized implements, and there is a marked drop in the
692 quantitative and qualitative importance of LCTs, following the tendency observed in
693 other final Middle Pleistocene assemblages (Monnier, 2006; Nicoud, 2013; Monnier and
694 Missal, 2014). For instance, handaxes lack the final refinement and standardization seen

695 in those from Galería and Sima de los Huesos (García-Medrano et al., 2015). In parallel,
696 there is a typological expansion and diversification of light-duty tools, dominated by
697 sidescrapers, denticulates, points, and convergent tools. Although there is no size
698 standardization of these tools in Lower TD10.1, there is a significant relationship between
699 the raw material worked and the typology of the tool, pointing to a concordance between
700 raw material properties and functional requirements ($\chi^2 = 268.47$, $df = 180$, $p \leq 0.0001$).
701 The tool diversification in Lower TD10.1 is consistent with a residential occupation
702 model for the cave, where various functional and technical activities were developed, as
703 supported by the zooarcheological record and use-wear studies (Blasco et al., 2013b;
704 Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015; Pedergrana and Ollé, 2019). In contrast, the higher
705 incidence of retouched tools and the restricted typological diversification of Upper
706 TD10.1-A and Upper TD10.1-B are consistent with short-term, sporadic stays at the site,
707 possibly related to higher mobility patterns of these groups (i.e., Barton and Riel-
708 Salvatore, 2014). In this respect, the differences observed between Lower TD10.1 and
709 the later sets reflect different territorial strategies of the hominine groups. The
710 diversification and size reduction of the retouched implements is also a common feature
711 of other Early Middle Paleolithic sites such as Payre, Bolomor, Cuesta de la Bajada, and
712 the middle stratigraphic unit of Ambrona (Santonja and Pérez-González, 2006; Fernández
713 Peris, 2007; Moncel et al., 2009, 2011; Santonja et al., 2014; Baena et al., 2017).

714 The TD10.1 assemblages contain other progressive technical aspects complementary
715 to the lithic production processes. Although these are scarce from a quantitative
716 perspective, they are qualitatively significant as they represent the first appearance in the
717 Atapuerca records. These features are also identified in other European and Levantine
718 final Middle Pleistocene sites and considered special indicators of the Middle Paleolithic
719 technological background (e.g., Kuhn, 2013; Moncel et al., 2011, 2016, 2020).

720 One of the most outstanding elements of the Lower TD10.1 assemblage is the presence
721 of composite tools; these have deeper operational, behavioral, and even evolutionary
722 implications (Perreault et al., 2013; Rots, 2013). The endscraper from subunit TD10.2
723 (Fig. 12C), along with new evidences from the current use-wear studies, show that this
724 technical innovation had already become incorporated into MIS 11 hominine technology,
725 making this one of the oldest records in Europe. Composite tools and hafting are
726 traditionally regarded as major technological innovations of this period (Rodríguez-
727 Álvarez, 2004b; Rots, 2013), but other technical behavior is also evident: lithic recycling
728 and bone industry (e.g., Rosell et al., 2015; Amick, 2007; Parush et al., 2015).
729 Interestingly, some of these techniques are also recorded in the underlying TD10.2
730 subunit, including the use of bone retouchers, which point to a deeper basis of these
731 behaviors in the Gran Dolina record (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015, 2017).

732 The presence of recycling and bone industry is usually considered a casual and
733 opportunistic response to immediate requirements and linked to scarce raw materials and
734 short-term occupations (Amick, 2007; Rosell et al., 2011, 2015). However, in Lower
735 TD10.1 these elements are principally related to the highest-density levels, making them
736 consistent with long-term and domestic occupations (entailing a wide variety of
737 subsistence activities), which are prone to these kind of strategies (Vaquero et al., 2012a,
738 2015). In summary, the Lower TD10.1 recycling events may be both unplanned and
739 opportunistic reactions to exceptional requirements (i.e., bone retouchers), as well as a
740 planned strategy in anticipation of future needs (i.e., the use of hammerstones as cores)
741 related to residential and domestic activities. Interestingly, there is no evidence of fire
742 control by the latest Middle Pleistocene hominin groups that inhabited the Sierra de
743 Atapuerca, although it was an increasingly widespread technology in this period
744 (Gowlett, 2006; Roebroeks and Villa, 2011; Shimelmitz et al., 2014).

745 These technological innovations parallel increasingly complex subsistence strategies
746 (Kuhn, 2013; Moncel et al 2016; Villa, 2009). The zooarcheological data reveals certain
747 subsistence trends that are later fully realized in the European Middle Paleolithic. The
748 strategies of the hominins of TD10.1 included specialization in high-ranked prey,
749 transport decisions focused on high energy elements (marrow), and the opportunistic,
750 complementary use of other secondary taxa and megafauna (Rodríguez Hidalgo et al.,
751 2015, 2017). Additionally, the consumption of leporids and birds is evidenced in the top
752 of the Lower TD10.1 assemblage, as is the hunting of large carnivores (Blasco, 2011;
753 Blasco and Rosell, 2009; Blasco et al., 2013c).

754

755 *4.2. The Mode 2 to Mode 3 transition in Atapuerca and southwestern Europe*

756 The new technical elements of TD10.1 do not emerge suddenly and abruptly, which
757 would point to a marked technological or cultural replacement; the appearance is rather a
758 cumulative process marked by the progressive emergence of technological and
759 subsistence behaviors through the Atapuerca record (Blasco et al., 2013b, c; Ollé et al.,
760 2013; Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2015, 2017;). These complex behaviors later crystallize in the
761 Middle Paleolithic communities (Arsuaga et al., 2017; Navazo et al., 2017). This dynamic
762 is similar to that observed in other Western Europe archeological sites and sequences
763 (e.g., Moncel et al., 2011, 2012; Scott et al., 2011c; Blasco et al., 2013c; Hérison et al.,
764 2016a) but it is, interestingly, coetaneous to other records that retain distinct Acheulian
765 technological features (Santonja et al., 2016). On the contrary, in Levant the early Middle
766 Paleolithic assemblages meant a technological break with respect to the Acheulo-
767 Yabrudian (Zaidner and Weinstein-Evron, 2016; Meignen and Bar-Yosef, 2020).

768 In the upper part of the Gran Dolina sequence, the TD10 stratigraphic succession is
769 documented between the Mode 2 and incipient Mode 3 assemblages. Nonetheless, there

770 is a discrepancy in this linear/progressive model of technological transfer identified in the
771 archeological sequences of the Trinchera del Ferrocarril sites and the newly available
772 geochronological data. According to the new radiometric dates from the Galería complex,
773 the Acheulian GII and GIII assemblages are from the early MIS 9 (Demuro et al., 2014),
774 making them even younger than the transitional assemblages from the Gran Dolina-
775 TD10.1 subunit (Ollé et al., 2016). The interpretation of the technological evolution at
776 Galería (García Medrano et al., 2014, 2015; Ollé et al., 2013), as well some data from soil
777 stratigraphy and correlations of the stratigraphic discontinuities at the Galería and Gran
778 Dolina sites are more parsimonious with the previous TL dates (Berger et al., 2008;
779 Vallverdú, 2017). In addition, the TD10 technological trend itself shows an evolution
780 consistent with this model. The lithic assemblage from the TD10.3 subunit presents
781 typical Mode 2 characteristics, from which 14 handaxes, 3 cleavers and 1 pick (25.6% of
782 the shaped tools) were recovered, while the TD10.2 subunit (although reflecting a marked
783 specialization) is defined by core and flake technology and a notably decreased presence
784 of LCTs (Ollé et al., 2013). The developing geochronological (single grain TT-OSL and
785 pIR-IR) and technological studies will further elucidate the temporal relationship between
786 the Galería and Grand Dolina sequences.

787 The state of the final Middle Pleistocene Atapuerca records reflects the complexity in
788 the Mode 2 and Mode 3 transition in Western Europe (e.g., Moncel et al., 2012; Hérissou
789 et al., 2016). Indeed, the same picture can be observed among the Iberian archeological
790 sites (Álvarez-Alonso, 2014; Santonja et al., 2014; Rios-Garaizar et al., 2015; Sánchez
791 Yustos and Díez Martín, 2015; Rios-Garaizar, 2017). In Iberia, Early Middle Paleolithic
792 (EMP) assemblages appear during MIS 10–9, either at cave sites (Bolomor, TD10.1,
793 Cueva del Ángel), or open-air sites (Ambrona, Cuesta de la Bajada, Solana de
794 Zamborino), coexisting until MIS6 with other distinctly Acheulian records along the main

795 fluvial courses: Tajo, Duero, and Miño (Santonja and Villa, 2006; Fernández Peris, 2007;
796 Barroso Ruíz et al., 2011; Ollé et al., 2016; Méndez Quintas et al., 2018). For some
797 authors, this coexistence can be explained either by a change in the occupational patterns
798 of the habitable spaces (Chazan, 2009; Terradillos-Bernal and Díez-Fernández-Lomana,
799 2012) or as a reflection of the cohabitation of two technocomplexes with different cultural
800 and demographic roots. In that case, the European EMP sites are interpreted as an
801 autochthonous evolution of the Early Pleistocene core and flake assemblages (Mode 1;
802 Santonja et al., 2014, 2016).

803 Nevertheless, the archeological and paleoanthropological scenario for the European
804 Lower and Middle Pleistocene human settlement is more complex than traditionally
805 considered (Hublin, 2009; Bermúdez de Castro et al., 2013, 2016; Ollé et al., 2016). There
806 is an important gap between the 900–500 ka archeological records, characterized by a
807 significant drop in the density of archeological sites, simultaneous with the disappearance
808 of Mode 1 assemblages and the emergence of the Acheulian technocomplex in Europe
809 (Moncel et al., 2013; Mosquera et al., 2013, 2016; Vallverdú et al., 2014). In Atapuerca
810 this gap is recorded in the stratigraphic sequences of Gran Dolina and Sima del Elefante,
811 which present Early Pleistocene (TD6 in Gran Dolina and TE9 in Sima del Elefante) and
812 Middle Pleistocene (TD10 and TE18-19) occupations. The archeological (but neither
813 sedimentary, nor paleontological) hiatus identified in these sequences prevents us
814 establishing any continuity between these communities (Mosquera et al., 2013; de
815 Lombera-Hermida et al., 2015). According to paleoenvironmental reconstructions, this gap
816 cannot be explained by drastic changes in climate conditions (Rodríguez, 2004;
817 Rodríguez et al., 2011). Likewise, paleoanthropological approaches to the European
818 Pleistocene settlement remark on its discontinuous and complex character (Dennell et al.,
819 2011; Bermúdez de Castro et al., 2016).

820 In contrast, the final Middle Pleistocene sequences present stratigraphic and
821 archeological continuity between the Mode 2 and Mode 3 assemblages, but several
822 models can be considered to interpret this (Chazan, 2009; Moncel et al., 2016). Human
823 adaptive responses may be highly diverse and variable in different landscapes and
824 territories, leading to a mosaic transitional model (Straus, 2007, 2009; Moncel et al.,
825 2011). In addition, we must also bear in mind the heterogeneity and variability that define
826 European Mode 2 assemblages and even other factors such as site functionality,
827 radiometric methods, stratigraphic integrity, land use patterns and even geographical
828 isolation of populations (Scott et al., 2011a; Nicoud, 2013; Nicoud et al., 2016; Ashton et
829 al., 2016; Moncel and Schreve, 2016; Ollé et al., 2016). From the archeological point of
830 view, southern European sites yielding long occupational sequences show that the
831 technological elements defining the EMP appear progressively—not necessary linearly
832 or homogeneously—from a fully Acheulian technology, with subsequent consolidation of
833 the Middle Paleolithic trends. This is the case of the cave sites of Orgnac-3, Payre, TD10
834 of Gran Dolina, as well as other regions that host diachronous long settlements between
835 MIS 11 and MIS 6 (i.e., Somme valley; SE England; Moncel et al., 2005, 2011, 2012;
836 Valladas et al., 2008; Scott et al., 2011a; Moncel and Daujeard, 2012; Ollé et al., 2013;
837 Hopkinson, 2015; Hérison et al., 2016b; Lamotte and Tuffreau, 2016). In other
838 territories, marked landscape fluctuations may have triggered the movement and
839 replacement of populations with different knapping traditions (Ahston et al., 2006, 2016).
840 On the contrary, the stability of the landscape and paleoenvironmental conditions during
841 the Middle Pleistocene of Atapuerca may have favored the adaptation of the human
842 groups to the local landscape and their small-scale mobility. These could explain a local
843 evolution of Mode 2 and Mode 3 populations in Atapuerca, accordingly with the
844 technological trends observed in the upper units of Gran Dolina.

845

846 **5. Conclusions**

847 The TD10.1 subunit displays a technological consistency throughout its assemblages
848 reflecting the fact that the hominins who inhabited the upper levels of Gran Dolina shared
849 the same conceptual schemes. Nevertheless, they show a mixture of technical features.
850 On the one hand, some characteristics are seen in the Acheulian records of Galería (GII-
851 GIII) and Sima del Elefante (TE18-19): raw material diversification, predominance of
852 bifacial centripetal methods, increased small flake-tools, and the survival of LCTs. On
853 the other hand, the TD10.1 assemblages show certain technological shifts that would later
854 transition into the full Mode 3 technocomplex: 1) raw material optimization strategies
855 based on selection and transport criteria; 2) the importance of flake cores and tools, as
856 well as the spatial fragmentation of the ‘chaîne opératoire’; 3) the increased
857 hierarchization of the centripetal exploitation methods; 4) the appearance of classical
858 discoidal and predetermined and hierarchized methods (Levallois); 5) greater efficiency
859 in lithic production (higher ratio of cutting edge per kg of raw material); 6) a greater
860 typological diversification of light-duty tools; 7) the appearance of bone industry and
861 bone retouchers; 8) the appearance of hafting evidence and composite tool production;
862 and 9) higher flexibility and planning capacity with regard to functional needs (lithic
863 recycling).

864 These technological and subsistence innovations are accumulative with respect to the
865 Late Pleistocene records from Atapuerca. Some of these treatments are also seen in the
866 upper assemblage of Galería (GIII) and the TD10.2 subunit (bone retouchers, scant
867 LCTs), but the specialized character of the latter—a kill-site whose lithic record is based
868 almost exclusively on chert resources—hinders its direct technological comparison with
869 the TD10.1 assemblages. In the framework of western Europe, these elements appear

870 during MIS 11–9, anticipating the behavioral and technological trends that would later
871 define the Middle Paleolithic. Consequently, the lithic assemblages from the TD10.1
872 subunit are considered to represent the final stages of that technological process in the
873 Atapuerca record and can be ascribed to the Early Middle Paleolithic.

874 The trend does not imply any cultural or demographic change in the final Middle
875 Pleistocene communities from Atapuerca. In south-western Europe, this transitional
876 mosaic model, defined as a ‘neanderthalization’ process (Moncel et al., 2011), is
877 consistent with the paleoanthropological and genetic evolution observed. Some *Homo*
878 *heidelbergensis* specimens show morphological features closer to those of the Late
879 Pleistocene Neanderthal population (i.e., Sima de los Huesos, interestingly now removed
880 from this hypodigm; Arsuaga et al., 2014) than others (i.e., Mauer, Caune de l’Arago),
881 although a direct relationship among demes and technocomplexes cannot be inferred
882 (Arsuaga et al., 2014; Meyer et al., 2014, 2016; Bermúdez de Castro et al., 2018; Vialet
883 et al., 2018; Rosas et al., 2019). Consequently, considering the current archeological and
884 paleoanthropological evidence from the European late Middle Pleistocene, the most
885 parsimonious hypothesis is a mosaic-type evolution towards Mode 3 technocomplexes
886 throughout MIS 11–6 from cultural and technological bases already defined in the
887 Acheulian records from Western Europe, rather than from relict final Early Pleistocene
888 populations.

889

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902

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1535

1536 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

1537

1538 **Figure 1.** A) Location of Sierra de Atapuerca in the Iberian Peninsula and aerial view. B)
1539 Location of Gran Dolina and its relation to the levels of the karstic system. C) Section of
1540 the Railway Trench and caves (modified from Bermejo et al., 2017).

1541

1542 **Figure 2.** A) Stratigraphic section of Gran Dolina with the location of the main lithofacies
1543 and radiometric dates of TD10.1 (modified from Campaña et al., 2017): 1 = debris flow
1544 facies A-D; 2 = debris fall; 3 = chanel facies; 4 = mud flow; 5 = floodplain; 6 =

1545 decantation; 7 = fluvial facies A-B; 8 = speleothem; 9 = breakdown; 10 = phosphate
1546 accumulation; 11 = weathering detritus. B) Projection of the archeological levels on the
1547 Gran Dolina North section.

1548

1549 **Figure 3.** Horizontal general distribution of the lithic artifacts from Lower TD10.1 and
1550 Upper TD10.1-A and location of the W to E section (lines M-N) and N to S section (N-
1551 S.1, line 21; N-S.2, line 12) projected below. Color refers to the archeological
1552 assemblages.

1553

1554 **Figure 4.** A) Trifacial core on Neogene chert. B–D) Longitudinal and orthogonal cores
1555 on quartzite (C) and Neogene chert (B, D). E–H) Discoidal cores on Neogene chert (E,
1556 H), quartzite (F), sandstone (G). Panel D belongs to Upper TD10.1-A.

1557

1558 **Figure 5.** A–E) Hierarchical centripetal cores with a preferential flaking surface on
1559 quartzite (A, C, E), Neogene chert (D), and quartz (B). F–H) Predetermined hierarchical
1560 centripetal cores on Cretaceous chert (F), Neogene chert (G) and quartzite (H).

1561

1562 **Figure 6.** Metric distribution of the complete flakes in the lithic assemblages according
1563 to their raw material (in mm).

1564

1565 **Figure 7.** Medium and large sized (A–C) and Levallois (D) flakes on quartzite from
1566 Upper TD10.1-A

1567

1568 **Figure 8.** Flakes and preferential flakes from Lower TD10.1 on Neogene chert (C, H),
1569 Cretaceous chert (I), quartzite (A, B, E–G), quartz (J), and sandstone (D, K).

1570

1571 **Figure 9.** Handaxes from Lower TD10.1 (A–D) and Upper TD10.1-A (E–G).

1572

1573 **Figure 10.** A, B) Quartzite cleavers from Lower TD10.1. C–R) Retouched flakes:
1574 denticulated tools, notches and sidescrapers on Neogene chert (C, E, Q), Cretaceous chert
1575 (D, F–H, O, P), quartzite (I, J, R), quartz (K, L), and sandstone (M, N).

1576

1577 **Figure 11.** A–D) Sidescrapers with stepped retouch on quartzite (A, B), Neogene chert
1578 (C), and Cretaceous Chert (D). E–K) Pointed and convergent tools on quartzite (E–G),
1579 Neogene chert (I–K), and Cretaceous chert (H).

1580

1581 **Figure 12.** A) ATA00-TD10-N20-66: use-wear related to hide scraping on one of the
1582 lateral edges (1, 2) and hafting evidence in the form of thinning and microabrasion and
1583 crushing on the proximal edge (3, 4). Original magnifications: 1) 40×; 2, 3) 1000×; 4)
1584 300×. B) ATA99-I15-92, TD10.1: evidence of hafting on the proximal part of a
1585 denticulate (3, 4), whose retouched tip was used in a sawing action on a hard material (1,
1586 2). Original magnifications: 1) 750×; 2) 2000×; 3) 200×; 4) 1000×. C) ATA93-H18-9,
1587 TD10.2: evidence of hafting on a Cretaceous chert end-scraper, in the form of flake
1588 thinning and hafting traces (3), associated to a well developed hide scraping polish on the
1589 distal edge (1, 2). Original magnifications: 1) 80×; 2) 250×; 3) 700×. In all cases, dots
1590 indicate areas exhibiting use-wear, whereas crosses illustrate where the traces associated
1591 with the handle were recorded.

1592

1593 **Figure 13.** A) Refitted core and flakes on quartzite. The core and initial flake show
1594 intense percussion marks on their cortical reserves (REM_3; Lower TD10.1). B ,C)

1595 Flakes on quartzite showing percussion marks on their dorsal ridges. D, E) Cores on
1596 quartzite showing percussion marks on their prominent ridges.

1597

1598 **Figure 14.** A) ATA'00-M13-45, Lower TD10.1: bone retoucher showing lateral retouch.

1599 B) ATA'04-K21-763: bone retoucher showing pits and scores. C) Detail of the Neogene

1600 chert embedded in its surface (photo by A. Rodríguez-Hidalgo). D, F) Quartzite shaped

1601 flakes showing marginal retouch and step terminations. E) Experimental quartzite shaped

1602 using a bone retoucher. Note the step terminations and the scalar superimposition.

1603

		Unknapped pebbles and cobbles				Cores			Shaped tools			Shaped T/Cores				Products		Indet/natural Frag.		TOTAL	%	
		nBa	nBb	nBc	nBd	1GNBE	2GNBE	FNBE	1GNBC	2GNBC	FNBC	2GNB	PB	FBP	Frag. Of BP	Frag.	nat. Frag.	Indet.				
Neogene chert						5	3	2	22			2	140	12	32	20	159		397	54,46		
%						1,26	0,76	0,50	5,54			0,50	35,26	3,02	8,06	5,04	40,05					
Cretaceous chert						1				6			18	2	7	1			35	4,80		
%						2,86				17,14			51,43	5,71	20,00	2,86						
Chert (indet)									2			1	13			4	5	20		45	6,17	
%									4,44			2,22	28,89			8,89	11,11	44,44				
Sandstone		4	2	2				1			2	5			21	3	11	4	6	18	79	10,84
%		5,06	2,53	2,53				1,27			2,53	6,33			26,58	3,80	13,92	5,06	7,59	22,78		
Quartzite		4	6	4	1	4	2				9	3	1	72	24	16	7	2	2	157	21,54	
%		2,55	3,82	2,55	0,64	2,55	1,27				5,73	1,91	0,64	45,86	15,29	10,19	4,46	1,27	1,27			
%		FG					1	1			1	2			29	4	1			40	5,49	
%		MG					2,50	2,50			2,50	5,00			72,50	10,00	2,50					
%		CG					3	2	1	1	2			3					12	1,65		
%		25,00	16,67	8,33	8,33	16,67								25,00								
%		Indet*					1	1	1				8	29	9	8	4	2	63	8,64		
%		1,59	1,59	1,59							12,70	46,03	14,29	12,70	6,35	3,17						
Quartz						1	2				1	1			4	1			10	1,37		
%						10,00	20,00				10,00	10,00			40,00	10,00						
%		NN													1			1	0,14			
%															100,00							
%		NS													2			4	0,55			
%															25,00							
%		SN													50,00							
%															1			1	0,14			
%		SS													100,00							
%		Indet*													1			4	0,55			
%															25,00			25,00				
Limestone		5																6	0,82			
%		83,33																16,67				
Other rocks																						
%																						

TOTAL	13	8	6	2	12	6	2	2	45	4	4	268	42	70	38	8	199	729
%	<i>1,78</i>	<i>1,10</i>	<i>0,82</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>1,65</i>	<i>0,82</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>6,17</i>	<i>0,55</i>	<i>0,55</i>	<i>36,76</i>	<i>5,76</i>	<i>9,60</i>	<i>5,21</i>	<i>1,10</i>	<i>27,30</i>	

Table 1. Lithic categories and raw materials at the TD10.1-A assemblage. Italics refer to percentages. (*Indet pieces or smaller than 20 mm).

	Unknapped pebbles and cobbles				Cores			Shaped tools			Shaped T. /Cores		Products				Indet/natural Frag.		TOTAL	%	
	nBa	nBb	nBc	nBd	1GNBE	2GNBE	FNBE	1GNBC	2GNBE	FNBC	1GNB	2GNB	PP	FPB	Frag. of PB	Frag.	nat. Frag.	Indet.			
Neogene chert					1				3	1			20	1	3	15		28	72	52,1	
%					<i>1,39</i>				<i>4,17</i>	<i>1,39</i>			<i>27,78</i>	<i>1,39</i>	<i>4,17</i>	<i>20,83</i>		<i>38,89</i>	<i>100,00</i>		
Cretaceous chert													4	1	1				6	4,35	
%													<i>66,67</i>	<i>16,67</i>	<i>16,67</i>				<i>100,00</i>		
Chert (indet)													2			3		5	10	7,25	
%													<i>20,00</i>			<i>30,00</i>		<i>50,00</i>	<i>100,00</i>		
Sandstone					1				2				2		1	5		2	5	18	13,0
%					<i>5,56</i>				<i>11,11</i>				<i>11,11</i>		<i>5,56</i>	<i>27,78</i>		<i>11,11</i>	<i>27,78</i>	<i>100,00</i>	
Quartzite		4							2				15	2	4	1			28	20,2	
%		<i>14,29</i>							<i>7,14</i>				<i>53,57</i>	<i>7,14</i>	<i>14,29</i>	<i>3,57</i>			<i>100,00</i>		
FG													1		1				2	1,45	
%													<i>50,00</i>		<i>50,00</i>						
MG		2											1						3	2,17	
%		<i>66,67</i>											<i>33,33</i>						<i>100,00</i>		
CG		2												1					3	2,17	
%		<i>66,67</i>												<i>33,33</i>							
Indet*									2				13	1	3	1			20	14,4	
%									<i>10,00</i>				<i>65,00</i>	<i>5,00</i>	<i>15,00</i>	<i>5,00</i>			<i>100,00</i>		
Quartz															1				1	0,72	
%															<i>100,00</i>						
NN															1				1	0,72	
%															<i>100,00</i>						
NS																					
%																					
SN																					
%																					
SS																					
%																					
Indet*																					
%																					
Limestone													1						1	0,72	
%													<i>100,00</i>								
Other rocks													1			1			2	1,45	
%													<i>50,00</i>			<i>50,00</i>					
TOTAL		4			2				7	1			45	4	10	25		2	38	138	100,0
%		<i>2,90</i>			<i>1,45</i>				<i>5,07</i>	<i>0,72</i>			<i>32,61</i>	<i>2,90</i>	<i>7,25</i>	<i>18,12</i>		<i>1,45</i>	<i>27,54</i>	<i>100,00</i>	

Table 2. Lithic categories and raw materials at the TD10.1-B assemblage. Italics refer to percentages. (*Indet pieces or smaller than 20 mm).

	Unknapped pebbles and cobbles				Cores			Shaped tools			Shaped T. /Cores		Products				Indet/natural Frag. nat.		TOTAL	%
	nBa	nBb	nBc	nBd	1GNBE	2GNBE	FNBE	1GNBC	2GNBC	FNBC	1GNB	2GNB	PB	FPB	Frag. of PB	Frag.	Frag.	Indet.		
Neogene Chert					56	72	4	1	262	12	2	8	4338	638	1343	530		3775	11041	51,30
%					<i>0,51</i>	<i>0,65</i>	<i>0,04</i>	<i>0,01</i>	<i>2,37</i>	<i>0,11</i>	<i>0,02</i>	<i>0,07</i>	<i>39,29</i>	<i>5,78</i>	<i>12,16</i>	<i>4,80</i>		<i>34,19</i>		
Cretaceous chert					19	4	4	1	106	6		1	846	141	211	68		26	1433	6,66
%					<i>1,33</i>	<i>0,28</i>	<i>0,28</i>	<i>0,07</i>	<i>7,40</i>	<i>0,42</i>		<i>0,07</i>	<i>59,04</i>	<i>9,84</i>	<i>14,72</i>	<i>4,75</i>		<i>1,81</i>		
Chert (Indet)						1			3	1	3	1	117	16	27	22		445	636	2,96
%						<i>0,16</i>			<i>0,47</i>	<i>0,16</i>	<i>0,47</i>	<i>0,16</i>	<i>18,40</i>	<i>2,52</i>	<i>4,25</i>	<i>3,46</i>		<i>69,97</i>		
Sandstone	9	3	26	13	17	13	5	5	89	2		3	1512	413	677	285	9	836	3917	18,20
%	<i>0,23</i>	<i>0,08</i>	<i>0,66</i>	<i>0,33</i>	<i>0,43</i>	<i>0,33</i>	<i>0,13</i>	<i>0,13</i>	<i>2,27</i>	<i>0,05</i>		<i>0,08</i>	<i>38,60</i>	<i>10,54</i>	<i>17,28</i>	<i>7,28</i>	<i>0,23</i>	<i>21,34</i>		
Quartzite	9	13	31	27	27	21	2	4	200	10	7	2	1553	856	721	175	8	45	3711	17,24
%	<i>0,24</i>	<i>0,35</i>	<i>0,84</i>	<i>0,73</i>	<i>0,73</i>	<i>0,57</i>	<i>0,05</i>	<i>0,11</i>	<i>5,39</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>0,19</i>	<i>0,05</i>	<i>41,85</i>	<i>23,07</i>	<i>19,43</i>	<i>4,72</i>	<i>0,22</i>	<i>1,21</i>		
FG	1		2	1	13	9		1	75	5			140	120	63	5			435	2,02
%	<i>0,23</i>		<i>0,46</i>	<i>0,23</i>	<i>2,99</i>	<i>2,07</i>		<i>0,23</i>	<i>17,24</i>	<i>1,15</i>			<i>32,18</i>	<i>27,59</i>	<i>14,48</i>	<i>1,15</i>				
MG	4	7	8	7	10	6	1	1	39	3	7	2	133	89	42	9		4	373	1,73
%	<i>1,07</i>	<i>1,88</i>	<i>2,14</i>	<i>1,88</i>	<i>2,68</i>	<i>1,61</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>10,46</i>	<i>0,80</i>	<i>1,88</i>	<i>0,54</i>	<i>35,66</i>	<i>23,86</i>	<i>11,26</i>	<i>2,41</i>		<i>1,07</i>		
CG	4	2	12	15	2	3	1		3	1			38	17	9	7			114	0,53
%	<i>3,51</i>	<i>1,75</i>	<i>10,53</i>	<i>13,16</i>	<i>1,75</i>	<i>2,63</i>	<i>0,88</i>		<i>2,63</i>	<i>0,88</i>			<i>33,33</i>	<i>14,91</i>	<i>7,89</i>	<i>6,14</i>				
Indet*		4	9	4	2	3		2	83	1			1242	630	607	154	8	41	2789	12,96
%		<i>0,14</i>	<i>0,32</i>	<i>0,14</i>	<i>0,07</i>	<i>0,11</i>		<i>0,07</i>	<i>2,98</i>	<i>0,04</i>			<i>44,53</i>	<i>22,59</i>	<i>21,76</i>	<i>5,52</i>	<i>0,29</i>	<i>1,47</i>		
Quartz	1	3	1	2	2				26	5		4	289	132	143	114	8	10	740	3,44
%	<i>0,14</i>	<i>0,41</i>	<i>0,14</i>	<i>0,27</i>	<i>0,27</i>				<i>3,51</i>	<i>0,68</i>		<i>0,54</i>	<i>39,05</i>	<i>17,84</i>	<i>19,32</i>	<i>15,41</i>	<i>1,08</i>	<i>1,35</i>		
NN									9	1			28	28	20	6			92	0,43
%									<i>9,78</i>	<i>1,09</i>			<i>30,43</i>	<i>30,43</i>	<i>21,74</i>	<i>6,52</i>				
NS			1		1				12	2		1	49	44	21	23	1		155	0,72
%			<i>0,65</i>		<i>0,65</i>				<i>7,74</i>	<i>1,29</i>		<i>0,65</i>	<i>31,61</i>	<i>28,39</i>	<i>13,55</i>	<i>14,84</i>	<i>0,65</i>			
SN					1								5	2					8	0,04
%					<i>12,50</i>								<i>62,50</i>	<i>25,00</i>						
SS													1						1	0,00
%													<i>100,00</i>							
Indet*	1	3		2					5	2		3	206	58	102	85	7	10	484	2,25
%	<i>0,21</i>	<i>0,62</i>		<i>0,41</i>					<i>1,03</i>	<i>0,41</i>		<i>0,62</i>	<i>42,56</i>	<i>11,98</i>	<i>21,07</i>	<i>17,56</i>	<i>1,45</i>	<i>2,07</i>		
Limestone	3		2						1		2		10	3			1	2	24	0,11
%	<i>12,50</i>		<i>8,33</i>						<i>4,17</i>		<i>8,33</i>		<i>41,67</i>	<i>12,50</i>			<i>4,17</i>	<i>8,33</i>		
Other rocks													3			9	5	3	20	0,09
%													<i>15,00</i>			<i>45,00</i>	<i>25,00</i>	<i>15,00</i>		
TOTAL	22	19	60	42	121	111	15	11	687	36	14	19	8668	2199	3122	1203	31	5142	21522	
%	<i>0,10</i>	<i>0,09</i>	<i>0,28</i>	<i>0,20</i>	<i>0,56</i>	<i>0,52</i>	<i>0,07</i>	<i>0,05</i>	<i>3,19</i>	<i>0,17</i>	<i>0,07</i>	<i>0,09</i>	<i>40,28</i>	<i>10,22</i>	<i>14,51</i>	<i>5,59</i>	<i>0,14</i>	<i>23,89</i>		

Table 3. Lithic categories and raw materials at the Lower TD10.1 assemblage. Italics refer to percentages. (*Indet pieces or smaller than 20 mm).

		Length	Width	Thickness
Raw Material	KW-X2	24,288	23,625	21,96
	df	4	4	4
	p-value	6,99E-05	9,49E-05	2,04E-04
Method	KW-X2	19,934	15,428	13,447
	df	5	5	5
	p-value	0,001286	8,68E-03	0,01953

Table 4. Univariate analysis of the Lower TD10.1 cores according to their metric data, raw material and methods.

		TD10.1			Upper TD10.1-A		
		Length	Width	Thickness	Length	Width	Thickness
Sandstone	Mean	15,68	16,5	4,86	22,29	25,71	8,823
	Sd	11,608	12,565	3,993	12,01	16,56	7,31
	IQR	11	13	4	14	28	7
	Coef.						
	Var.	0,7399	0,7611	0,8209	0,5389	0,644	0,8282
	Min	1	1	1	6	7	1
	Max	82	76	31	49	58	32
	N	1302			17		
	Median	12	16,51	4	21	21	8
Quartz	Mean	13,72	13,07	5,16	19,33	14	10
	Sd	8,469	8,665	4,203	17,62	9	9,9849
	IQR	8	9	4,25	17	9	9,5
	Coef.						
	Var.	0,6173	0,662	0,814	0,9112	0,6428	9,849
	Min	2	3	1	5	5	2
	Max	50	48	24	39	23	21
	N	220			3		
	Median	11	10	4	14	14	7
Quartzite	Mean	17,81	18,15	5,71	31,77	31,84	9,31
	Sd	12,73	12,709	4,729	16,78	17,88	5,79
	IQR	14	14	6	23	24	9
	Coef.						
	Var.	0,7147	0,7	0,828	0,528	0,5617	0,6223
	Min	2	2	1	7	5	1
	Max	90	102	32	78	90	21
	N	1436			61		
	Median	13	14	4	28	28	8
Neogene Chert	Mean	16,33	15,4	5,21	35,59	31,84	10,93
	Sd	12,278	11,559	4,682	22,91	22,34	7,47
	IQR	12	13	5			
	Coef.						
	Var.	0,751	0,7505	0,899	0,6438	0,7017	0,6831
	Min	1	1	0	3	1	1
	Max	150	89	45	93	102	34
	N	3265			61		
	Median	13	12	4	29	26	9
Cretaceous Chert	Mean	14,81	14,27	4,31	29,76	24	8,18
	Sd	9,37	8,332	3,373	14,84	9,64	4,2
	IQR	10	10	4			
	Coef.						
	Var.	0,632	0,583	0,783	0,4987	0,4016	0,5139
	Min	2	1	1	10	3	1
	Max	62	55	25	59	46	17
	N	796			17		
	Median	12	12	3	27	23	8

Table 5. Metric features of the complete flakes from Lower TD10.1 and Upper TD10.1-A

	Gran Dolina TD10								Galería Complex							
	TD10-1a		TD10-1b		TD10-2		TD10		GIII		GII		Galería Complex			
	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB	T	T w nB		
Neogene chert	2,391	2,391	1,824	1,824	4,088	4,088	3,392	3,392	1,746	1,746	1,260	1,260	1,658	1,658		
Cretaceous chert	4,986	4,986	3,870	3,870	8,276	8,585	6,042	6,182	2,127	2,127	4,344	4,344	3,934	3,934		
Quartzite	1,232	2,634	467	1,331	811	-	867	1,950	472	998	452	1,067	463	1,053		
Quartz	565	565	-	-	-	-	1,302	1,302	-	-	-	-	1,469	2,008		
Sandstone	1,299	1,645	-	-	-	-	1,423	1,709	438	786	591	1,210	485	1,044		
Limestone	-	-	-	-	-	-	112	458	66	159	159	365	134	312		
Total	1,700	2,402	1,468	2,462	4,125	4,662	3,099	3,338	467	951	484	1,147	479	1,106		

Table 6: Length of cutting edge (mm) per kilogram related raw materials (PC: Pebble cores; PT: Pebble tools; F: Flake; FC: Flake core; FT: Flake tools; T: Total; T w H-M: without nB).

		TD10.1			Upper TD10.1-A		
		Lentgh	Width	Thickness	Length	Width	Thickness
Sandstone	Mean	54,39	35,91	14,89	55,6	40	14,2
	Sd	16,81	11,75	6,93	14,26	16,8	4,15
	Se (mean)						
	IQR	16.75	13,25	8	9	9	2
	Coef. Var.	0,3090609	0,3271	0,46549	0,2564	0,42019	0,29206
	Min	25	13	4	42	24	10
	Max	135	85	40	79	68	21
	N	80			5		
	Median	50	35	15	50	37	14
	SKEWNESS	1,6584	1,27497	1,2849			
Quartz	Mean	34,96	25,27	13,81	47	39	15
	Sd	10,07	8,42	4,49	n/a	n/a	n/a
	Se (mean)						
	IQR	9	9,5	6,5			
	Coef. Var.	0,2881	0,3331	0,3258			
	Min	15	10	5	47	39	15
	Max	66	47	23	1		
	N	26					
	Median	34	24	13,5	47	39	15
	SKEWNESS	10.404	0,96696	0,30507	n/a	n/a	n/a
Quartzite	Mean	49,09	33,99	15,68	46,28	18,71	15,14
	Sd	12,97	10,27	5,703	6,94	13,58	6,82
	Se (mean)						
	IQR	17,25	13	9	10,5	16	7,5
	Coef. Var.	0,2642	0,30205	0,36376	0,1501	0,3509	0,4502
	Min	20	14	2	40	26	5
	Max	82	80	35	57	64	25
	N	196			7		
	Median	47	34	15	44	35	15
	SKEWNESS	0,3868	0,78676	0,42965	n/a	n/a	n/a
Neogene chert	Mean	46,016	33,11	14,42	45,73	37,73	15,37
	Sd	14,28	10,72	6,51	18,33	14,21	8,57
	Se (mean)						
	IQR	17	15	8	16,5	16,5	11
	Coef. Var.	0,31044	0,32374	0,45157	0,40083	0,37651	0,5577
	Min	15	12	2	22	20	5
	Max	100	50	54	90	72	40
	N	247			19		
	Median	42	32	14	42	34	15
	SKEWNESS	0,9119	0,67861	1,32522	n/a	n/a	n/a
Cretaceous chert	Mean	38,24	25,91	12,51	36,8	25	11,8
	Sd	12,46	7,384	6,51	15,91	8,12	4,97
	Se (mean)						
	IQR	15	10	8	30	12	5
	Coef. Var.	0,3259	0,28495	0,43428	0,4324	0,32496	0,42117
	Max	82	50	30	54	35	18

N	104				5		
Median	37	25	12		33	22	13
SKEWNESS	0,75106	0,31974	0,76896	n/a	n/a	n/a	

Table 7. Metric dimensions of the retouched flakes, excluding LCT.